

De-dollarization and Foreign Policy: Perception of vulnerability and strategy within the BRICS framework

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Abstract

This article examines BRICS de-dollarization through Foreign Policy Analysis (FPA), arguing that it is not an automatic response to structural monetary asymmetries but a product of political interpretation. While the dollar's dominance creates objective vulnerabilities, de-dollarization emerges when leaders perceive monetary dependence as a strategic risk. Drawing on Sprout and Sprout, Snyder, Bruck and Sapin, and Jervis, the study distinguishes between structural conditions and their cognitive interpretation. BRICS initiatives, such as local currency trade and alternative financial institutions, are thus better understood as hedging strategies shaped by perceived vulnerability rather than attempts to overturn the global monetary order.

Keywords: BRICS+, Desdolarização; Sul Global, Política Externa

Introduction

The centrality of the dollar in the International Monetary System (IMS) constitutes one of the structural pillars of the contemporary global economic order. As Maurício Metri (2020, p. 720) argues, the dollar system should not be understood merely as a technical-financial arrangement, but as a geopolitical mechanism that grants the United States structural advantages and the capacity to project power in the monetary and financial realms. In this sense, dollar hegemony organizes international hierarchies and conditions the room for maneuver of peripheral and emerging economies.

In recent years, however, BRICS [2] countries have intensified initiatives aimed at reducing dependence on the dollar, such as strengthening the New Development Bank (NDB), promoting the use of local currencies in bilateral trade, and advocating for greater monetary diversification. According to Cassa and Cossul (2025, p. 362), such movements can be interpreted as part of a broader effort led by the Global South to challenge the international financial architecture, as Batista Júnior argues.

BRICS countries share a longstanding dissatisfaction with the existing international monetary and financial architecture. In these early decades of the twenty-first century, the reasons for dissatisfaction have only increased. Financial, economic, and political instabilities have risen dramatically, yet the West shows no signs of making the necessary adaptations and concessions to accommodate BRICS and other emerging market nations. Moreover, the dysfunctionality of the dollar-based international monetary system, which dates back to the 1960s, has become increasingly evident (Batista Júnior, 2024, p. 7–8, our translation).

Although this literature highlights the structural asymmetries of the international monetary system, it tends to privilege explanations centered on economic structure, devoting less attention to the decision-making process and to the specifically political dimension involved in the formulation of such strategies. The mere existence of monetary hierarchies does not automatically generate policies of contestation. As Sprout and Sprout suggest (Ferreira, 2020, pp. 137–138), it is necessary to distinguish between the operational environment, that is, the objective conditions of the international system, and the psychological environment, which corresponds to how decision-makers perceive and interpret those conditions. The centrality of the dollar constitutes a structural fact; its transformation into a foreign policy problem depends on interpreting this dependence as a strategic vulnerability.

From the perspective of Foreign Policy Analysis, it is argued that the de-dollarization agenda within BRICS emerges when dependence on the dollar comes to be perceived as a potential risk to state autonomy. Recent events associated with the strategic use of economic and financial interdependence, such as the tariffs imposed by President Donald Trump, reinforce this interpretation, contributing to the political construction of monetary vulnerability. Thus, rather than being a mere reflection of dollar hegemony, de-dollarization can be understood

A political and economic coalition aimed at strengthening its member states. It is currently composed of Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, the United Arab Emirates, Ethiopia, Indonesia, and Iran.

as a foreign policy strategy oriented toward the pursuit of greater autonomy in an international system marked by monetary asymmetries.

This article adopts a qualitative and interpretative approach, combining bibliographic review and documentary analysis. It establishes a theoretical dialogue between the International Political Economy literature on monetary power and dollar hegemony and the framework of Foreign Policy Analysis, particularly the contributions of Sprout and Sprout, Snyder, Bruck and Sapin, and Robert Jervis. This framework is then applied to the BRICS case. The objective is not to test hypotheses through quantitative modeling, but to identify the analytical mechanism that connects monetary structure, perception of vulnerability, and the formulation of foreign policy strategy. It is therefore an explanatory study of an analytical-conceptual nature, seeking to demonstrate how the interpretation of monetary asymmetries conditions the political construction of de-dollarization as a strategic agenda.

The Structure of the International Monetary System and Vulnerability to the Dollar

The centrality of the dollar in the International Monetary System constitutes a structural element of the contemporary economic order. Since the post-Second World War period, the U.S. currency has consolidated its position as the primary store of value, medium of international payment, and unit of account in global transactions, thereby shaping an asymmetric monetary architecture. As Metri (2020, p. 721) argues, this centrality is not limited to a technical or operational function, but should be understood as a geopolitical mechanism that sustains the privileged position of the United States within the international hierarchy. In this sense, the dollar system operates as a structure of power that enables the United States to externalize costs, finance deficits, and exert influence over global financial flows, transforming the currency into an instrument of strategic projection. However, serving as the issuer of the world's primary reserve currency also carries inherent costs. The Triffin Dilemma, introduced by Robert Triffin in 1950, suggests that to ensure adequate global liquidity, the reserve-currency country must run continuous balance-of-payments deficits, creating structural tensions within the international monetary system (Resende, 2024).

This interpretation is supported by literature emphasizing the hegemonic character of the dollar within the IMS. Souza et al. (2024, p. 14) highlight that the predominance of the U.S. currency in international reserves, trade transactions, and global financial markets reproduces structural dependencies, particularly for emerging economies. The concentration of liquidity and financial instruments denominated in dollars generates systemic incentives for its continued use, while simultaneously limiting viable short-term alternatives. Such an arrangement reinforces asymmetries and reduces the room for maneuver of countries whose international integration depends on access to foreign markets and financing in foreign currency. As Eichengreen argues,

“[...] it is not obvious why the dollar—the currency of an economy that no longer accounts for the majority of the world’s industrial production—should be used to invoice and settle most of the world’s international transactions. Nor is it clear why the dollar should continue to constitute the predominant share of central bank and government reserves. As the global economy becomes multipolar, logic suggests that its monetary system should likewise follow this trend and become multipolar. At the very least, this reasoning implies that the dollar will have to share its international role.” (Eichengreen, 2011, p. 119, our translation).

In this context, de-dollarization initiatives emerge as attempts to mitigate such vulnerabilities and expand margins of autonomy, particularly as countries in the Global South seek to reduce their exposure to structural asymmetries. The strengthening of mechanisms such as the New Development Bank (NDB) and the promotion of local currencies in bilateral trade reflect efforts toward diversification and rebalancing within a monetary order still heavily centered on the dollar.

However, although the structure of the international monetary system generates objective incentives and constraints, it does not automatically determine political responses. The existence of monetary asymmetries and external vulnerabilities constitutes the operational environment in which states operate; the transformation of these conditions into a foreign policy agenda depends on how they are interpreted by decision-makers. It is at this point that Foreign Policy Analysis provides the theoretical tools to understand how dependence on the dollar can be politically constructed as a strategic vulnerability.

The Structure Of The International Monetary System And Vulnerability To The Dollar

If the centrality of the dollar constitutes the operational environment that structures monetary hierarchies and conditions margins of autonomy, the transformation of this condition into a political agenda depends on how it is perceived by decision-makers. Foreign Policy Analysis (FPA) provides a fundamental theoretical framework for understanding this movement, as it shifts the explanatory focus from systemic structure to the processes of interpretation and situational definition that precede state action.

States do not respond directly to structures, but to their cognitive representations of those structures, which highlights the importance of understanding the specificities of decision-makers (Ferreira, 2020, p. 25). In this sense, dependence on the dollar may exist as a structural fact; however, it only becomes a foreign policy problem when it is interpreted as a risk to strategic autonomy or as a potential instrument of financial coercion. Vulnerability, therefore, is not merely a material condition, but also a political construction.

This emphasis on perceptual mediation is reinforced by Snyder, Bruck, and Sapin (Ferreira, 2020, p. 24), who argue that foreign policy decisions derive from the “definition of the situation” elaborated by governing elites. The international structure provides constraints

and incentives, but it is decision-makers who assign meaning to these elements and organize them into diagnoses of threats and opportunities. Thus, the centrality of the dollar may be interpreted either as a source of systemic stability and predictability or as a mechanism of asymmetry and strategic dependence. The choice between these interpretations directly influences the type of policy adopted.

Robert Jervis (Ferreira, 2020, p. 28) further deepens this dimension by arguing that perceptions, prior beliefs, and images of other actors shape how the international environment is understood. Historical experiences, crisis events, and episodes involving the strategic use of economic interdependence tend to reinforce particular interpretations and consolidate narratives of threat. When financial and commercial measures come to be perceived as instruments of geopolitical pressure, monetary dependence may be reinterpreted as a strategic vulnerability, encouraging initiatives aimed at diversification and risk reduction.

Applied to the debate on de-dollarization, the FPA lens allows us to understand that the BRICS agenda does not automatically result from the asymmetries of the international monetary system, but from the political construction of those asymmetries as a problem. The centrality of the dollar remains a constant structural element; what varies is how it is interpreted by decision-makers and incorporated into the definition of the strategic situation. De-dollarization, in this sense, emerges as a response formulated on the basis of perceived vulnerability and the pursuit of greater autonomy within an international context marked by asymmetric interdependence.

Perception and Decision-Making in Foreign Policy Analysis

The existence of structural asymmetries in the International Monetary System does not, in itself, automatically determine the adoption of policies of contestation or monetary diversification. The transformation of dependence on the dollar into a foreign policy agenda depends on how this condition is interpreted by decision-makers. At this point, Foreign Policy Analysis provides central theoretical tools by shifting the explanatory focus from systemic structure to the processes of perception and situational definition that precede state action.

Thus, dependence on the dollar may be structurally constant, but its conversion into a strategic problem depends on how decision-makers interpret that dependence (Ferreira, 2020, p. 24). When perceived as a source of vulnerability or as a potential instrument of coercion, it may motivate strategies aimed at reducing exposure. In the context of the international monetary system, dollar hegemony may be defined either as a guarantee of stability or as a mechanism of asymmetric dependence. This definition is crucial for understanding the choice between accommodation and contestation.

Robert Jervis (1976), in turn, analyzes decision-making by emphasizing how historical experiences, such as crises, financial sanctions, or geoeconomic disputes, can reinforce the perception that economic instruments are used as tools of political power, thereby consolidating a sense of vulnerability. From this perspective, dependence on the dollar ceases to be merely a structural fact and becomes framed as a strategic risk. Foreign policy then emerges as an attempt to mitigate perceived risks, even when structural conditions remain relatively constant.

Applied to the debate on de-dollarization, the FPA lens allows us to understand that the BRICS agenda does not result mechanically from U.S. monetary hegemony. The centrality of the dollar constitutes the operational environment; the decision to seek alternatives stems from how this centrality is defined by decision-makers as a problem of autonomy and economic security. De-dollarization, therefore, should be analyzed as the product of cognitive and political processes that transform structural asymmetries into foreign policy strategies aimed at reducing vulnerability and expanding room for maneuver in the international system.

De-Dollarization in BRICS as a Foreign Policy Strategy

The de-dollarization agenda within BRICS may be interpreted as a foreign policy strategy oriented toward the pursuit of greater autonomy in the context of an international monetary system structured around the centrality of the dollar, yet dependent on how this structure is incorporated into states' strategic definitions. As Metri (2020, p. 732) argues, the dollar system not only organizes global financial flows but also sustains a hierarchy that enhances the United States' capacity for influence. In this context, dependence on dollar-denominated assets, reserves, and transactions may be perceived as a source of vulnerability, particularly when associated with the strategic use of economic interdependence. The centrality of the U.S. currency thus ceases to be merely a functional mechanism of the system and comes to be interpreted as a potential instrument of political pressure.

Zein et al. (2025, p. 2) identify motivations that extend beyond strictly economic considerations, including concerns about systemic stability, decision-making autonomy, and the reduction of exposure to external shocks. Although the authors acknowledge practical limitations and structural obstacles to replacing the dollar, their conclusions reinforce the idea that the movement should be understood as an effort toward diversification and risk mitigation, rather than as an abrupt rupture with the existing monetary order.

From Jervis's perspective (Ferreira, 2020, p. 28), this dynamic can be understood as the result of processes of perception and interpretation. When events associated with the geopolitical use of financial instruments reinforce the image of the system as politicized and potentially coercive, dependence on the dollar tends to be reinterpreted as a latent threat. This reading contributes to the formulation of strategies aimed at expanding room for maneuver and reducing perceived vulnerabilities. De-dollarization, therefore, does not necessarily imply

the replacement of the dollar as the dominant currency, but rather represents an attempt to dilute risks and broaden alternatives.

In this sense, the BRICS de-dollarization agenda can be understood as a foreign policy strategy constructed through the interaction between structure and perception. Dollar hegemony constitutes a systemic condition; its conversion into motivation for political action depends on its interpretation as a strategic problem. By mobilizing financial and diplomatic instruments directed toward monetary diversification, BRICS countries are not merely responding to structural constraints, but articulating a project of autonomy shaped by specific perceptions of vulnerability and power within the international system.

Conclusion

By integrating International Political Economy and Foreign Policy Analysis, it becomes clear that de-dollarization does not automatically result from dollar centrality, but emerges when decision-makers interpret this centrality as a strategic vulnerability. While the monetary structure is a constant condition, its transformation into a political problem depends on how governing elites define the situation. In this sense, BRICS de-dollarization should be understood as a foreign policy strategy aimed at increasing autonomy within a context of asymmetric interdependence, rather than as an immediate rupture with the existing order. It represents a diversification strategy designed to expand room for maneuver in a system perceived as politicized and hierarchical. Monetary disputes, therefore, must be analyzed as foreign policy phenomena, since international autonomy is shaped not only by material constraints but also by political interpretations of risk and opportunity.

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